

Sağlıkta kalite standartlarında eğitimin yeri

The place of education in health quality standards

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ABSTRACT

Aim: Healthcare Quality Standards serve as a guide for many different types of healthcare facilities. The purpose of this study is to identify the standards required for training within the Healthcare Quality Standards and to categorize the training recipients and the training programs themselves.

Materials and Methods: The Healthcare Quality Standards sets were examined; specifically, the training management sections and the standards and evaluation criteria that include the phrases "training should be provided," "training should be organized," and "information should be provided" were included in the study. The Hospital Set, the most comprehensive set, was chosen as the basis due to its similarity to the other sets; 523 standards and 1599 evaluation criteria were examined. Within this set, the items requiring training were identified, target groups were identified, and training sessions were categorized and presented in a table.

Results: Training was determined to be required on 22 of the 523 standards and 186 of the 1599 evaluation criteria in the Hospital Set. Nine of these 22 standards cover training for patients/families, and 13 for staff. Of the 186 evaluation criteria for which training was required, 130 were planned for staff and 56 for patients/families. The categorical distribution of training is presented in detail in the study.

Conclusion: Healthcare Quality Standards mandate the provision of planned training to all personnel and patients/families across all levels. The Training Management section under the Corporate Services heading emphasizes the need to identify training needs and evaluate the effectiveness of the training provided. This highlights the importance of involving both service providers and service users in the establishment and sustainability of a quality management system. The detailed inclusion of the Training Management section in the standards clearly demonstrates the importance SKS places on training.

Key Words: Quality standards in healthcare, education, patient education, employee education

ÖZ

Giriş: Sağlıkta Kalite Standartları farklı türdeki pek çok sağlık tesisine yol gösteren bir rehber niteliğindedir. Çalışmanın amacı; Sağlıkta Kalite Standartları içerisinde eğitim verilmesi istenen standartların ortaya çıkarılması, eğitim alacakların ve eğitimlerin kategorize edilmesinin sağlanmasıdır.

Gereç ve Yöntem: Sağlıkta Kalite Standartları setleri incelenmiş; özellikle eğitim yönetimi bölümleri ile "eğitim verilmelidir", "eğitim düzenlenmelidir" ve "bilgilendirme yapılmalıdır" ifadelerinin yer aldığı standart ve değerlendirme ölçütleri çalışmaya dahil edilmiştir. En kapsamlı set olan Hastane Seti, diğer setlerle benzerlik göstermesi nedeniyle temel alınmış; 523 standart ve 1599 değerlendirme ölçütü incelenmiştir. Bu set içinde eğitim verilmesi gereken maddeler belirlenmiş, hedef gruplar çıkarılmış ve eğitimler kategorize edilerek tablo hâlinde sunulmuştur.

Bulgular: Hastane Seti'ndeki 523 standarttan 22'sinde ve 1599 değerlendirme ölçütünden 186'sında eğitim verilmesi gerektiği belirlenmiştir. Bu 22 standarttan 9'u hasta/hasta yakınına, 13'ü ise çalışanlara yönelik eğitimleri kapsamaktadır. Eğitim istenen 186 değerlendirme ölçütünün ise 130'u çalışanlara, 56'sı hasta/hasta yakınlarına yönelik olarak planlanmıştır. Eğitimlerin kategorik dağılımı çalışmada ayrıntılı biçimde sunulmuştur.

Sonuç: Sağlıkta Kalite Standartları, tüm boyutlarda çalışanlara ve hasta/hasta yakınlarına planlı bir şekilde eğitim verilmesini zorunlu kılar. Kurumsal Hizmetler başlığı altındaki Eğitim Yönetimi bölümünde, eğitim ihtiyacının belirlenmesi ve verilen eğitimlerin etkinliğinin değerlendirilmesi gerektiği vurgulanmaktadır. Bu durum, kalite yönetim sisteminin oluşturulması ve sürdürülebilirliğinde hizmet verenler ile hizmet alanların sürece dahil edilmesinin önemini ortaya koymaktadır. Eğitim Yönetimi bölümünün standartlarda ayrıntılı şekilde yer alması, SKS'nin eğitime verdiği önemi açıkça göstermektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sağlıkta kalite standartları, eğitim, hasta eğitimi, çalışan eğitimi

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INTRODUCTION

“Quality and Accreditation for Qualified and Effective Healthcare Services,” part of the Health Transformation Program, is among our Ministry’s priority objectives (1). This program, which restructures all elements of healthcare services, is organized into various components and subcomponents (2).

Healthcare quality standards have been established to improve quality in all healthcare institutions in Turkey, address identified deficiencies, and provide guidance to healthcare professionals from a different perspective. These standards have become essential to providing significant benefits to healthcare professionals, patients, and their families (3). As in all other fields, the focus on quality in healthcare services is increasing daily. Hospitals are among the institutions most affected by this development, as a large portion of healthcare services are provided there. These institutions, where diverse professional groups work together, have a highly complex structure. Certain standards are needed to ensure that the services provided are delivered with high quality throughout the process, eliminating errors and uncertainties. (4)

Healthcare Quality Standards are developed by the Ministry of Health, General Directorate of Health Services, Department of Quality in Healthcare, Accreditation, and Employee Rights. Healthcare Quality Standards are a set of mandatory guidelines for healthcare facilities, including hospitals, oral and dental health centers, dialysis centers, medical centers, and emergency healthcare services. These guidelines clearly outline the necessary procedures and guide institutions. The set examined in this study is the Version 6.1 Hospital Set, published in 2020.

The SKS Hospital set includes 5 dimensions, 46 sections, 523 standards, and 1,599 evaluation criteria (5). The training management section is located within the Corporate Services dimension and consists of 6 standards and 17 evaluation criteria. The training management section requires that SKS-related training be provided to employees and patients/patient relatives within a plan and program, and that the effectiveness of the training be evaluated.

Training helps employees adapt to new conditions and understand the goals and values of the organization they work in (6). The primary goal of in-service training is to provide individuals with the fundamental knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to perform their duties effectively and accurately (7).

Patient education is a process conducted between patients and healthcare professionals. It aims to create behavioral changes by improving the knowledge, perception, attitudes, and skills of patients and their families, so that they can adapt to the treatment and care process and contribute to the improvement of their health. This education enables patients and their families to make informed decisions and develop self-care skills. (8)

The purpose of the study is to reveal the standards required for training within the Quality Standards in Healthcare and to categorize the training recipients and the training provided.

The originality of the study is that it examines all SKS sets and makes inferences from the set, and there is no study on educational management in the SKS set in the literature.

The study consists of three parts. The first part includes an introduction that provides

general information, the second part includes the materials, methods, and findings, and the third part includes discussion and conclusion sections.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

There are five sets of Healthcare Quality Standards: Hospital, ADSM/H, Dialysis, Prehospital Health Services, and Medical Center Sets. All SKS sets were examined, and the standards and evaluation criteria for “training should be provided,” “training should be organized,” “information should be provided,” and “information should be provided” within the sets, as well as those mentioned in other sections, were examined and included in the study. Because the Hospital Set is the most comprehensive set and the training management sections within

the other sets share similar characteristics, the Hospital Set was selected for this study.

The dimensions and sections of the Hospital Set were examined, the 1599 evaluation criteria in the set were reviewed, and the standards and evaluation criteria that indicated the need for training were revealed.

In this study, the standards for which training/information was requested were identified in number, by dimension and by section. The resulting standards and evaluation criteria were then filtered to determine which groups were intended to receive training/information.

Following the review, the required training standards and evaluation criteria were categorized. For the training required for employees, the following were taken into

Table 1. Corporate services-training required standard numbers

Dimension	No	Department Name	Total S* and EC** (n)		Education/ Information S* ve EC** (n)	
			S* (n)	EC** (n)	S* (n)	EC** (n)
Corporate Services	1	Corporate Structure	8	23	1	2
	2	Quality Management	14	33		3
	3	Document Management	5	15		1
	4	Risk Management	5	13		1
	5	Corporate Efficiency	5	8		
	6	Unwanted Event Reporting System	5	12	1	3
	7	Disaster and Emergency Management	14	61	1	8
	8	Management Of CBRN Hazards	6	11		3
	9	Education Management	6	17	2	3
	10	Social Responsibility	3	3		1
	Total	71	196	5	25	

* S: Standard Clause, **EC: Evaluation Criteria

Table 2. Patient and employee-focused services-training standard requirements

Dimension	No	Department Name	Total S* and EC** (n)		Education/Information S* ve EC** (n)	
			S*(n)	EC**(n)	S* (n)	EC** (n)
Patient and Employee-Oriented Services	1	Patient Experience	14	43	1	9
	2	Access to Services	5	17		3
	3	End-of-Life Services	8	13		1
	4	Healthy Working Life	12	35		6
		Total	39	108	1	19

* S: Standard Clause, **EC: Evaluation Criteria account: "information should be provided," "documentation training should be provided," "training on the safe use of devices should be provided," "personal development," and "training should be provided in schools." "Awareness training" included training intended for all employees, and "in-service training" included training intended to be planned specifically for specific departments (such as radiology unit or emergency room staff). The training required to be given to patients/patient relatives was handled within the scope of "education" or "information" as clearly stated in the standard, and in the evaluation criteria, in addition to "education" and "information", the category of "providing education in schools" was added as in the "Community Mental Health Services" section.

RESULTS

In the tables below, the 5 dimensions included in the Quality Standards in Healthcare Hospital set are grouped, and the number of standards and evaluation criteria for the sections included in the dimensions and the standards for which training and information are required to be provided within each section are shown.

The Corporate Services dimension is presented in Table 1. When the table is examined, it is stated that there are 10 sections within the corporate services dimension, a total of 71 standards and 196 evaluation criteria in each section, and training should be provided in 5 of the 71 standards and 25 of the 196 evaluation criteria.

Table 2 shows the Patient and Employee-Focused Services dimension. Upon examination of the table, it is stated that there are four sections in the Patient and Employee-Focused Services dimension, with a total of 39 standards and 108 evaluation criteria in the sections, and that training is required for one of the 39 standards and 19 of the 108 evaluation criteria.

Table 3 shows the Health Services dimension. Upon examination of the table, it is stated that there are 24 sections in the Health Services dimension, with a total of 325 standards and 1,019 evaluation criteria in the sections, and that training is required for 15 of the 325 standards and 123 of the 1,019 evaluation criteria.

Table 3. Health services-education required standard numbers

Dimension	No	Department Name	Total S* and EC** (n)		Education/ Information S* ve EC** (n)	
			S*(n)	EC**(n)	S* (n)	EC**(n)
Health Services	1	Patient Care	26	80		11
	2	Medication Management	15	48		1
	3	Infection Prevention and Control	14	33	2	4
	4	Cleaning, Disinfection and Sterilization Services	15	70		3
	5	Transfusion Services	9	38		5
	6	Therapeutic Apheresis Services	11	30		1
	7	Radiation Safety	18	49	1	7
	8	Emergency Department	14	49	1	3
	9	Operating Room	11	30		2
	10	Intensive Care Unit	13	31		1
	11	Neonatal Intensive Care Unit	16	46		5
	12	Maternity Services	7	29	1	7
	13	Dialysis Unit	15	27	2	2
	14	Psychiatry Services	15	53	2	7
	15	Community Mental Health Services (CMHS)	16	50		4
	16	Biochemistry Laboratory	15	49	1	11
	17	Microbiology Laboratory	16	53	1	12
	18	Pathology Laboratory	16	67		8
	19	Tissue Typing Laboratory	14	43	1	11
	20	Chemotherapy Services	8	29	1	4
	21	Organ and Tissue Transplantation Services	14	46	1	4
	22	Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation Services	7	25	1	4
	23	Palliative Care Clinic	10	24		1
	24	Home Health Services	10	20		5
	25	Total	325	1019	15	123

* S: Standard Clause, **EC: Evaluation Criteria

Table 4. Support services-education required standard numbers

Dimension	No	Department Name	Total S* and EC** (n)		Education/ Information S* and EC** (n)	
			S*(n)	EC**(n)	S* (n)	EC**(n)
Support Services	1	Facility Management	16	60		2
	2	Hospitality Services	16	54		3
	3	Information Management System	17	59		7
	4	Material and Equipment Management	18	51		4
	5	Medical Records and Archiving Services	7	13		
	6	Waste Management	5	22	1	2
	7	Outsourcing	3	4		
		Total	81	264	1	18

* S: Standard Clause, **EC: Evaluation Criteria

Table 4 shows the Support Services dimension. Upon examination of the table, it is stated that there are 7 sections in the Support Services dimension, with a total of 81 standards and 264 evaluation criteria in the sections, and that training is required for 1 of the 81 standards and 18 of the 264 evaluation criteria.

Table 5 shows the Support Services dimension. Upon examination of the table, it can be seen that there is one section in the Indicator Management dimension, which contains seven standards and 12 evaluation criteria. While the standards do not mention the provision of training, one of the 12 evaluation criteria states that training must be provided.

Table 5. Indicator management-education required standard numbers

Dimension	No	Department Name	Total S* and EC** (n)		Education/ Information S* and EC** (n)	
			S*(n)	EC**(n)	S* (n)	EC**(n)
Indicator Management	1	Monitoring Indicators	7	12		1

* S: Standard Clause, **EC: Evaluation Criteria

Table 6. Number of standard items required for training by dimension

No	Dimension	Total S* and EC** (n)		Education/Information S* and EC** (n)	
		S*(n)	EC**(n)	S* (n)	EC**(n)
1	Corporate Services	71	196	5	25
2	Patient and Employee-Oriented Services	39	108	1	19
3	Healthcare Services	325	1019	15	123
4	Support Services	81	264	1	18
5	Indicator Management	7	12		1
	Total	523	1599	22	186

* S: Standard Clause, **EC: Evaluation Criteria

Table 6 lists the total number of standard-evaluation criteria and the number of standard-evaluation criteria for which training is required, broken down by dimension. The Healthcare Quality Standards Hospital Set includes 523 standards and 1,599 evaluation criteria, of which 22 standards and 186 evaluation criteria involve providing training to staff or patients/patient relatives.

For the standard items and evaluation criteria for which training/information is required, which are discussed in 5 dimensions and specified in numbers in 46 sections, shown in the tables above, firstly the group to be trained or informed (employees or patients/patient relatives) was determined and then categorized according to the type of training and presented in the graphs below.

Fig 1. Training types and numbers

When Fig 1 is examined, it is seen that 22 items among the standard items are related to the provision of training, 13 of which are related to the need to provide training to employees and 9 to patients/patient relatives.

Fig 2. Types and numbers of training for employees

When Fig 2 is examined, it is seen that 130 items among the evaluation criteria are related to training of employees, and 66 of these trainings are covered within the scope of in-service training.

Fig 3. Types and numbers of training for patients/relatives

When Fig 3 is examined, it is seen that 56 items among the evaluation criteria are related to providing education to patients/patient relatives, and 43 of these educations are addressed within the scope of informing.

DISCUSSION

All processes related to teaching patients the rules of a healthy life, instilling health-protection habits, and coping skills with health problems have become the starting point of patient education. Instilling changes in patients' health-related behaviors and the ability to lead healthy lives are possible through education provided to patients and their families (9). Informing the patient about the procedures to be performed according to Quality Standards in Healthcare, including them in the process or educating and informing the patient about how to proceed during the discharge process after the procedure will contribute positively to the treatment process. In the study, in the Hospital set, patients/patient relatives were asked to be informed in 5 items and to be trained in 4 items among the standard items, and within the evaluation criteria, training in 13 criteria (1 of which was training in schools) and information in 43 items were requested.

When the descriptive characteristics of intern physicians regarding patient safety are examined, it is seen that the training provided

within the scope of Quality Standards in Healthcare leads to positive developments in the process of identifying and verifying patient identity and the awareness of intern physicians on the subject increases significantly (10). They should organize regular trainings for their employees on quality management and SKS and constantly update their knowledge on these subjects (11). The evaluation criterion in the training management section is "training should be provided to the personnel to cover the processes related to SKS on the basis of the unit in which they work." In the study, it was requested that the employees in the hospital set be given information in 3 items, in-service training in 4 items and awareness training in 6 items among the standard items.

The structure, content, processes, and outcomes of healthcare services, particularly hospital services, are complex, unlike other service sectors. Furthermore, the direct relationship between the healthcare system and human health means that any error can cost human life. The high cost of medical equipment, along with healthcare personnel, increased healthcare provision, and the necessity of keeping up with evolving technology all contribute to increased costs (12). Considering that the safety culture can be achieved through the integration of education and the field, it is thought that the foundations of patient safety can be laid and the errors that may be encountered during the process of identifying and verifying the patient identity can be minimized by regularly carrying out training plans, which are the main points for the patient identification process, or by including "Quality Standards Training in Healthcare" in the training curriculum (10). Staff training is essential to minimize employee-related errors and provide flawless healthcare services. To ensure the desired level of quality, it is crucial that this training be planned and implemented periodically,

documented, and that all employees participate (13). In the study, the evaluation criteria for the employees in the Hospital set were as follows: document training in 5 criteria, awareness training in 28 criteria, in-service training in 66 criteria, informing in 25 criteria, safe use of devices in 5 criteria, and personal development training in 1 criteria. The Quality Standards in Healthcare include the evaluation criterion that “records of training provided should be accessible in the personnel file.”

In-service training, which involves the participation of all employees, is a prerequisite for the error-free and flawless delivery of healthcare and other services. Based on this, it can be argued that the training of all personnel within healthcare institutions should be prioritized and supported. Therefore, it is crucial that this training be regularly planned, provided, and documented. Furthermore, institutions must take responsibility for the “qualification” of their personnel, supporting both internal and external training, and providing appropriate conditions for this (14). It has been stated that in order for training to be carried out regularly, it should be carried out within the planned program established by the Training Management department in the Corporate Services dimension.

In today’s environment, where high service quality is expected, human capital constitutes a significant cost, yet it is crucial for healthcare institutions to be effective and efficient. Healthcare personnel are the most fundamental actors in providing high-quality healthcare services, and their level of competence, including knowledge and skills, is invaluable to the institution (13). The Health Quality Standards include the standard article “in-service training should be organized for employees” and the evaluation criterion “in-service training should be organized for employees” depending on this article.

CONCLUSION

The Healthcare Quality Standards Hospital Set includes 523 standards and 1599 evaluation criteria. The study found that 22 of the 523 standards and 186 of the 1599 evaluation criteria were related to the need for training.

When examined on a size basis;

- 5 standards and 25 evaluation criteria in the Corporate Services Dimension,
- 1 standard and 19 evaluation criteria in the Patient and Employee-Focused Services Dimension,
- 15 standards and 123 evaluation criteria in the Health Services Dimension,
- 1 standard in the Support Services Dimension, 18 evaluation criteria,
- In the Indicator Management Dimension, it has been determined that training is required in 1 evaluation criterion.

The groups that were required to receive training were determined within the study, and it was observed that the standards and evaluation criteria indicated that training should be given to employees or patients/patient relatives.

As a result of the review, the standards and evaluation criteria for which training was required were categorized, and the target audience for training was determined to be employees and patients/patient relatives. The trainings were as follows:

- Information
- Awareness Training
- In-Service Training
- Document Training
- Safe Use of Devices

- Personal Development,

Categorized as Education in Schools (Community Mental Health Services).

Of the 523 standard articles, 22 pertain to training. Nine of these articles address the need for training for patients/relatives, and 13 pertain to training for employees. Of the nine articles required to be provided to patients/relatives, five pertain to information, and four pertain to training. Of the 13 required training for employees, six pertain to awareness training, four pertain to in-service training, and three pertain to information.

It is seen that 130 of the 1599 evaluation criteria are related to training of employees, 66 of these trainings are within the scope of in-service training, 28 are awareness training, 25 are information, 5 are document training, 5 are safe use of devices and 1 is within the scope of personal development.

It is seen that 56 of the 1599 evaluation criteria are related to providing education to patients/patient relatives, 43 of these educations are addressed within the scope of informing, 12 of them are addressed within the scope of training, and 1 of them is addressed within the scope of providing education in schools.

Healthcare Quality Standards stipulate that training and information should be provided across all dimensions. The need for this training to be provided to employees and patients/families within a planned program is outlined in the Training Management section of the Corporate Services dimension. The training management section requires evaluation of the effectiveness of the training. It also states that the training needs of employees and patients/families should be identified within the training management section.

In conclusion, the inclusion of both service providers and service recipients in the process is crucial for establishing and maintaining a quality management system in healthcare. It has been specified that information should be provided to which groups of people will receive training at which stages of implementation of the standards. The inclusion of training in the standard clauses, evaluation criteria, and the inclusion of a “Training Management” section detailing how this training will be conducted clearly demonstrate the importance that the Healthcare Quality Standards place on training.

- Trainings required to be carried out within the Quality Standards in Healthcare must be implemented meticulously as they will affect patient and employee safety.
- The effectiveness and efficiency of training should be evaluated and prioritized. The root causes of training deemed ineffective should be investigated, and improvement activities should be planned.
- Planning should be made outside of the training specified in the standards, taking into account the training needs of patients and employees.

REFERENCES

1. Ministry of Health, General Directorate of Health Services, Department of Quality, Accreditation And Employee Rights In Health. Accessed date: 03 Aug 2025. Available from: <https://shgmkalitedb.saglik.gov.tr/TR-8785/turkiye-saglikta-kalite-sistemi.html>
2. Çavmak Ş, Çavmak D. Historical development of health services in Turkey and the health transformation program. *J Health Manage.* 2017;1(1):48–57.

3. Kavuncubaşı Ş, Yıldırım S. Hospital and health institutions management. Chapter 1: Environment. 4th ed. Ankara: Siyasal Bookstore; 2015.
4. Coşkun S. Comparison of TS EN 15224-2012 health services quality management standard with other quality standards in health services. [PhD thesis]. Istanbul: Okan University, Institute of Health Sciences; 2017.
5. Ministry of Health, General Directorate of Health Services, Department of Quality, Accreditation and Employee Rights in Health. Version 6.1 hospital set. Ankara; 2020. p. 1–516.
6. Sokoh GC. In-service training in the Nigerian public service: its implication for national development. *J Public Adm Finance Law*. 2021; (22):81–92.
7. Iqbal N, Khan MM, Mohmand YT, Mujtaba BG. The impact of in-service training and motivation on job performance of technical & vocational education teachers: role of person-job fit. *Public Organ Rev*. 2019;19:529–48.
8. Lacroix A, Assal JP. Therapeutic education of patients. Paris; 2000.
9. Ozden M. Health education textbook. Ankara: Positive Design Publishing; 2003.
10. Çamlıca T, Kaya V, Kılıncı G, et al. The effect of healthcare quality standards training on intern physicians' knowledge of patient identification and verification. *Hacettepe Health Administration J*. 2024;27(2):225–236.
11. Kılıç U, Uzun H. Quality management in health services: Elazığ example. *Firat Univ J Harput Res (FÜHAD)*. 2023;10(20):83–111.
12. Taş D. A study on the measurement of health service quality. *J Perform Qual Health*. 2012;(4):79–102.
13. Altındış S, Ergin A. Health personnel training in the context of quality. *Sakarya Med J*. 2018;8(1):157–169.
14. Hoş C. Overcoming the difficult in the health sector: accreditation in the health sector. *Süleyman Demirel Univ J Soc Sci Inst (CIEP Special Issue)*. 2016;499–533.